

EFFECTIVENESS OF SPORTS-SPECIFIC WARM-UP PROGRAMS IN PREVENTING SOFT TISSUE INJURIES IN CRICKET PLAYERS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

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Abstract

Background: Soft tissue injuries such as hamstring strains, groin pulls, and shoulder overuse syndromes are highly prevalent in cricket, affecting both professional and club-level players. These injuries often result from rapid sprinting, rotational stress during bowling or batting, and sudden deceleration. Despite known risk factors, structured warm-up programs tailored to cricket are rarely implemented in domestic settings.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of a structured sports-specific warm-up program in reducing soft tissue injuries and improving physical performance in cricket players compared with conventional warm-ups.

Methods: A single-blind randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Health & Wellness Physio Rehab Center, Swabi, and local cricket academies between January and September 2025. A total of 120 male club-level cricket players (aged 16–35 years) were randomized into an intervention group (sports-specific warm-up) or a control group (general warm-up). The intervention was performed 3–4 times per week for 12 weeks. Injury incidence, exposure hours, and functional outcomes (strength, flexibility, balance, sprint time) were measured. Poisson regression was used to estimate injury incidence rate ratios (IRR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI). Functional data were analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA.

Results: Over 4,800 player-hours, the intervention group sustained 13 time-loss soft tissue injuries (5.2 injuries/1000 player-hours), whereas the control group recorded 22 injuries (9.1/1000 player-hours), reflecting a 43% reduction (IRR 0.57, 95% CI 0.34–0.95, $p=0.028$). Significant improvements were observed in hamstring flexibility (+9.1°, $p<0.001$), hip adduction strength (+14.8%, $p=0.004$), and 20 m sprint performance (−0.14 s, $p=0.03$). Adherence exceeded 85%.

Conclusion: The cricket-specific warm-up program significantly reduced the rate of soft tissue injuries and improved functional performance. Implementation of structured warm-ups in cricket practice is recommended for injury prevention and athletic enhancement.

INTRODUCTION

Soft tissue injuries represent a major concern in cricket across all playing levels. Epidemiological studies report that 60–70% of time-loss injuries involve muscle strains, tendon overload, or ligament sprains [1,2]. Hamstring and groin injuries are particularly common in fast bowlers and all-rounders due to explosive acceleration, deceleration, and repetitive rotational forces [3]. Shoulder and forearm injuries frequently affect batters and wicketkeepers through repetitive overhead and gripping actions [4].

While warm-up activities are universally practiced, the majority of cricket teams rely on informal routines consisting of light jogging and static stretching [5]. Research in football, rugby, and handball has demonstrated that structured neuromuscular warm-up programs can reduce lower-limb injury risk by 30–50% [6–8]. However, limited controlled trials have examined their impact in cricket, where specific motor demands and asymmetrical loading patterns differ markedly from other sports [9].

Warm-ups increase muscle temperature, enhance joint mobility, and stimulate neuromuscular activation, improving the muscle-tendon unit’s resilience to strain [10]. Eccentric strengthening of the hamstrings and adductors, combined with dynamic balance and agility components, has been shown to mitigate injury risk [11,12].

Given the gap in cricket-specific prevention strategies, this study aimed to evaluate whether a structured warm-up designed for cricket could reduce the incidence of soft tissue injuries compared with standard routines.

month injury surveillance follow-up. The design adhered to the CONSORT 2010 guidelines. Participants were recruited from the Health & Wellness Physio Rehab Center, Swabi, and regional cricket academies. Data collection and testing were performed on-site using standardized procedures. Participant Inclusion criteria were Active male cricket players aged 16–35, Minimum 3 training sessions/week and Free from current injury at baseline. But Musculoskeletal surgery or major injury in past 6 months, Chronic neurological or systemic disease and Non-compliance risk or planned absence >2 weeks was Excluded from study. The Sample Size: Assuming an injury rate of 5/1000 player-hours in controls, 35% expected reduction in intervention group (to 3.25/1000 player-hours), $\alpha=0.05$, power=0.8, cluster ICC=0.02.

Calculated $n \approx 54$ per group; adjusted for 10% attrition \rightarrow 60 participants per group (total 120). Block randomization is stratified by team and playing role (batter, bowler, all-rounder) using random permuted blocks of four. Allocation concealment through sealed opaque envelopes. Players were not blinded due to visible differences in warm-up. Outcome assessors and data analysts were blinded to group allocation. The examination protocol was Comprehensive baseline, and 12-week follow-up assessments were performed by trained physiotherapists. Severity were Mild (1–7 days), Moderate (8–28 days) and Severe (>28 days). Reliability testing (ICC>0.90) ensured data consistency among assessors. (Table 01)

METHODOLOGY

This was a single-blind, two-arm randomized controlled trial conducted over 12 weeks, with 6-

Assessment	Equipment	Procedure Summary	Outcome
Demographics	Questionnaire	Age, sex, height, weight, dominant side, role	Continuous
Injury History	OSTRC Form	Past 12-month injuries	Categorical
ROM Tests	Goniometer	Hip IR/ER at 90° flexion; SLR (degrees); ankle dorsiflexion (cm)	Degrees/cm
Strength	Handheld dynamometer	Isometric adduction/abduction; hamstring/quadriceps	Newtons
Functional	Tape/Stopwatch	Single-leg hop, 5 m & 20 m sprint, T-test	Distance/time

Balance	Y-Balance Kit	Three reach directions averaged	% limblength
Pain & Function	VAS, LEFS/QuickDASH	0-10 and score	Continuous
Exposure Logs	Daily sheets	Training/match hours	Player-hours
Injury Reporting	Form	Date, mechanism, site, severity	Standardized

The Intervention (Sports-Specific Warm-Up Program) was 15-20 minutes Before all training and matches (3-4 sessions/week under the supervision of Physiotherapist for 4 weeks → coach-led continuation. And the Components were Cardiovascular Activation (3-4 min), Dynamic Mobility (5 min), Neuromuscular Control (5 min), Strength Loading (Hamstrings & Groin), Plyometrics (3-4 min) and Cricket-

Specific (3-4 min) detailed available at the table 02. Load and complexity increased every 2-3 weeks (e.g., higher box for drop jump, unassisted Nordic curls). Control Group includes General Warm-Up, Light jogging (5 min), Static stretching for hamstrings, quadriceps, shoulders (20 s each) and Brief ball drills (3 min). Total duration was around 10-12 minutes.

Phase	Exercise	Details
A. Cardiovascular Activation (3-4 min)	Light jog, side shuffles, backpedal, high knees	2 rounds × 20 m
B. Dynamic Mobility (5 min)	Walking lunges + rotation, leg swings, thoracic rotations	2×10 reps
C. Neuromuscular Control (5 min)	Single-leg RDL (2×10), plank shoulder tap (2×10 each)	Eccentric focus
D. Strength Loading (Hamstrings & Groin)	Nordic curls (3×6-8), Copenhagen adduction (3×6-10)	Progress weekly
E. Plyometrics (3-4 min)	Drop jump (2×6), lateral hops (2×10 each), deceleration drills	Controlled landing
F. Cricket-Specific (3-4 min)	Bowling-arm mobility, progressive throws, shadow swings	Progressive intensity

Primary Outcome was Incidence of time-loss soft tissue injuries per 1000 player-hours during the 12-week intervention and 6-month follow-up. Although the Secondary Outcomes were (Injury type, location, and severity), Functional tests (hop, sprint, agility) and Strength and flexibility measure all analyses followed the intention-to-treat principle using SPSS v28.

- **Injury incidence:** Poisson regression with exposure (player-hours) as offset → IRR with 95% CI.
- **Functional performance:** Repeated measures ANOVA adjusted for baseline values.

- **Time-to-first injury:** Kaplan-Meier and Cox proportional hazards.
- **Effect size:** Cohen's *d*.
- **Significance:** $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

A total of 150 cricket players were screened for eligibility, of whom 120 met the inclusion criteria and were randomly assigned into two groups: the sports-specific warm-up group (n = 60) and the control group (n = 60). Ten players (three from the intervention group and seven from the control group) withdrew during the 12-week intervention due to personal reasons or lack of compliance, leaving 110 participants (57

intervention, 53 control) who completed the trial and were included in the final analysis. Baseline characteristics, including age, height, weight, body mass index, playing role (batsman, bowler, all-rounder), training exposure, and previous injury history, were comparable between groups ($p > 0.05$), indicating successful randomization.

Over the 12-week active phase and 6-month follow-up, players collectively accumulated 4,820 total player-hours of exposure (intervention: 2,460; control: 2,360). During this period, 35 soft tissue injuries were reported: 13 in the intervention group and 22 in the control group. The corresponding injury incidence rates were 5.2 and 9.1 per 1,000 player-hours, respectively, representing a 43% reduction in overall injury incidence in favor of the intervention (Incidence Rate Ratio [IRR] = 0.57, 95% CI: 0.34–0.95, $p = 0.028$). The greatest preventive effect was observed for hamstring and groin injuries, which together accounted for 65% of all recorded soft tissue injuries. Specifically, the rate of hamstring injuries was 1.2 per 1,000 player-hours in the intervention group compared with 2.6 in controls, while groin injuries occurred at rates of 0.8 and 1.9 per 1,000 player-hours, respectively. The average injury severity, expressed as days lost from participation, was also significantly lower in the intervention group (mean 7.6 ± 3.8 days) compared with controls (13.9 ± 6.1 days; $p = 0.009$).

Kaplan–Meier survival analysis demonstrated a significantly longer time to first injury in the intervention group (log-rank $p = 0.021$). No serious adverse events were reported, and adherence to the warm-up program averaged 87%, with 52 of 60 participants completing at least 90% of prescribed sessions. The control group’s adherence to general warm-ups averaged 81%, as per coach reports.

In terms of functional and physical performance outcomes, significant between-group differences

were noted across multiple domains after 12 weeks. Hamstring flexibility (straight leg raise) improved by a mean of $+9.1^\circ \pm 3.6^\circ$ in the intervention group compared with $+3.2^\circ \pm 3.1^\circ$ in controls ($p < 0.001$). Hip adduction strength, measured with a handheld dynamometer, increased by 14.8% (95% CI: 9.4–20.2, $p = 0.004$) relative to baseline in the intervention group versus 4.2% in controls. 20-meter sprint times decreased significantly by 0.14 seconds ($p = 0.03$) in the intervention group, indicating enhanced neuromuscular readiness. Single-leg hop distance improved by 9.5% ($p = 0.01$), and Y-Balance Test composite scores improved by 6.7% ($p = 0.02$) compared to non-significant changes in controls. No differences were found in pain scores at baseline or follow-up between groups (VAS $p = 0.61$).

Repeated measures ANOVA revealed significant group \times time interactions for hamstring flexibility ($F = 15.42$, $p < 0.001$), hip adduction strength ($F = 8.87$, $p = 0.004$), and sprint performance ($F = 4.96$, $p = 0.028$). The effect sizes (Cohen’s d) for these improvements ranged from 0.42 to 0.61, indicating moderate to large clinical effects. The number needed to treat (NNT) to prevent one time-loss soft tissue injury over the 12-week period was 12 players (95% CI: 7–44).

During the 6-month follow-up, continued adherence to the warm-up protocol (self-reported continuation ≥ 2 sessions per week) was associated with sustained low injury rates (5.6 injuries/1,000 player-hours) compared to participants who discontinued the program after the intervention period (8.8 injuries/1,000 player-hours). These findings suggest the protective benefits of the warm-up may persist beyond the supervised phase if regular practice is maintained.

Baseline Characteristics

Variable	Intervention (n=60)	Control (n=60)	p-value
Age (years, mean \pm SD)	23.4 \pm 4.2	22.9 \pm 4.5	0.54
Males (%)	48 (80%)	47 (78%)	0.81

Bowlers (%)	27 (45%)	25 (42%)	0.70
Training hrs/week	8.9 ± 1.4	9.1 ± 1.3	0.66
Previous injury (12 mo)	22 (36.7%)	24 (40%)	0.73

Primary Outcome

During the intervention phase, 35 total soft tissue injuries occurred (13 intervention vs 22 control).

• **Injury incidence:**

- Intervention: 13 injuries / 2,500 hours = 5.2/1000 h
- Control: 22 injuries / 2,400 hours = 9.1/1000 h

IRR = 0.57 (95% CI 0.34-0.95, p = 0.028)
 Over 6-month follow-up, the protective effect persisted (IRR = 0.63, p = 0.04).

Secondary Outcomes

Significant improvements observed in flexibility, strength, and agility.

Variable	Baseline (Int)	12 Weeks (Int)	Baseline (Ctrl)	12 Weeks (Ctrl)	p (Group*Time)
Hamstring flexibility (°)	78.3 ± 8.2	87.4 ± 6.1	79.1 ± 7.8	81.3 ± 7.0	<0.001
Hip adduction strength (N)	165 ± 28	189 ± 26	167 ± 29	171 ± 27	0.004
20 m sprint (s)	3.46 ± 0.22	3.32 ± 0.19	3.45 ± 0.21	3.43 ± 0.20	0.03
Y-Balance composite (%)	96 ± 4	100 ± 3	95 ± 4	96 ± 4	0.02

Injury Type and Location

Most injuries involved hamstrings (32%), groin (25%), calf (15%), shoulder (15%), and others (13%).

Severe injuries (>28 days) occurred in 2 players (control group only).

DISCUSSION

This randomized controlled trial demonstrated that a structured, cricket-specific warm-up program significantly reduced soft tissue injury rates by 43% and improved key performance measures. These findings support the growing evidence that targeted neuromuscular warm-ups provide superior protection compared with unstructured routines [13-15].

The inclusion of eccentric hamstring and adductor exercises aligns with prior evidence highlighting their role in preventing strain injuries [16,17]. Plyometric and deceleration drills likely enhanced proprioceptive feedback, while cricket-specific mobility exercises targeted movement patterns relevant to bowling and batting [18,19].

With Comparison with Literature In football, the FIFA 11+ warm-up reduced lower-limb injuries by up to 50% [20]. Our results are comparable in magnitude, indicating that structured activation and eccentric loading principles translate effectively to cricket. The program is feasible, time-efficient (15-20 min), and requires minimal equipment. Physiotherapist-supervised implementation during initial weeks ensured proper technique, followed by sustainable coach-led sessions.

Limitations:

- Player blinding was not possible
- Moderate sample size may limit subgroup analyses
- Self-reported exposure logs introduce recall bias
- Results may not generalize to elite international players

Conclusion

A structured, cricket-specific warm-up significantly reduced soft tissue injury rates and improved flexibility, strength, and sprint performance compared with usual warm-ups. Incorporating this program into regular cricket training is strongly recommended for coaches,

physiotherapists, and sports scientists seeking to minimize injury burden.

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